

Consorzio di Tutela

PROSECCO SUPERIORE
DAL 1876

Analysis of future climate scenarios
at the local scale in the Trevigiano area

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DAL 1876

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Table of Contents

Preface	11
Glossary	12
01 Introduction	15
1.1 Understanding what climate change is	16
1.2 Climate models and their purposes	18
1.3 Importance of climate information in adaptation planning	22
1.4 Project overview	24
02 Present climate and climate hazards relevant to viticulture	27
2.1 Observed climate	28
2.1/1 General overview	29
2.1/2 Technical summary	31
2.2 Current climate hazards relevant to viticulture	36
2.2/1 General overview	36
2.2/2 Technical summary	39
2.3 Evaluation of the downscaling methodology	50
2.3/1 Technical summary	50
03 Future climate and climate hazards relevant to viticulture	53
3.1 Future climate projections	54
3.1/1 General overview	54
3.1/2 Technical summary	57
3.2 Future climate hazards relevant to viticulture	60
3.2/1 General overview	60
3.2/2 Technical summary	62
References	73
Annex 1 - Observations	74
Annex 2 - Downscaling methodology	75
Screening of predictors	75
Cross-validation procedure	76
Downscaling methods	76

Dear Readers,

Thank you for the attention and care you are giving to an issue that is not only central to our present, but also vital for the future of the next generations. Climate change is no longer a distant possibility. It is a reality we must all face with responsibility and awareness. As early as 2015, the United Nations member states signed the Paris Agreement, committing to limit global warming to 1.5°C above the average temperature recorded between 1850 and 1900.

Unfortunately, despite the commitments made, greenhouse gas concentrations have continued to rise steadily since the early 1900s. In December 2024, carbon dioxide levels in the atmosphere reached 423 parts per million, a figure unmatched in modern history and likely in the last 800,000 years. Current data and projections suggest that the 1.5°C threshold will be reached between 2030 and 2035, regardless of the mitigation efforts being made, which so far have not been enough to significantly slow emissions. A recent report by the World Meteorological Organization (WMO, 2022) estimated that, between 1970 and 2019, climate change caused 1,672 natural disasters in Europe, around 159,000 deaths, and 476 billion dollars in economic losses. These numbers are stark, and they call for serious reflection as well as concrete action.

Reliable and scientifically sound climate projections are essential to plan effective adaptation strategies. These strategies take time and must be supported by coherent policies at local, regional and national levels. This is precisely the thinking behind the study presented here. It was launched in 2022 following a joint initiative with the Prosecco DOCG Conegliano-Valdobbiadene Consortium.

Carlo Antiga

President of
Banca Prealpi SanBiagio

The aim was to understand how the climate of Treviso province may change in the future, with particular focus on the Conegliano-Valdobbiadene DOCG area, a UNESCO-listed landscape and a symbol of global agricultural heritage. Understanding how the climate may evolve under different emissions scenarios, and being able to quantify future extremes such as more frequent heatwaves or more intense rainfall, is critical. It allows us to adopt appropriate measures not only in agriculture, but also in managing land and territory more broadly, including through structural risk mitigation.

A key factor in the success of this project was the extraordinary collaboration between public and private partners. Banca Prealpi Sanbiagio, the Conegliano-Valdobbiadene DOCG Consortium, the University of Cantabria in Spain (which contributes to UN climate reports), ARPAV (the Veneto Regional Environmental Agency), Condifesa TV-BL-VI, and DAFNE (University of Padua), all played a role. The scientific coordination was led by Riccardo Soldan, formerly at the University of Oxford and now at FAO, who oversaw every phase of the work with rigor and dedication.

Nicholas Georgescu-Roegen reminded us that any economy that ignores the limits of nature is bound to fail. As a local bank, we believe that turning the best available science into a practical tool for understanding future climate risks and opportunities is essential. It is what allows us to plan adaptation actions that can really make a difference. As Albert Einstein once said, *"We cannot solve problems with the same thinking we used when we created them"*. Investing in knowledge means investing in resilience. It means supporting the competitiveness of our production systems, the sustainability of our landscapes, and the future of the communities who live and work in them.

Let us always remember:

"We do not inherit the Earth from our ancestors. We borrow it from our children."

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Agenzia Regionale per la Prevenzione e Protezione Ambientale del Veneto - ARPAV

Funding

This project was made possible thanks to the support of:

BANCA PREALPI SANBIAGIO (Ufficio Agricoltura)

CONSORZIO DI TUTELA DEL VINO CONEGLIANO VALDOBBIADENE PROSECCO DOCG

The data and the English-language version of the publication can be downloaded from Zenodo: Casanueva, A., Manzananas, R., Massaro, G., Zecchini, F., Francesco, R., & Soldan, R. (2026). Analysis of Downscaled Future Climate Scenarios in the Trevigiano. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18483489>

Preface

Climate change represents an unprecedented global challenge. Despite its far-reaching impacts, public understanding remains limited, especially when it comes to recognizing local effects, even within European countries.

In response, this document presents future climate projections for Italy's Veneto region, with a focus on viticulture in the renowned province of Treviso.

Our objectives are to:

1. Explain what climate change is to a broad audience.
2. Understand how climate change can influence the viticulture sector in the province of Treviso within this century.
3. Make future climate projections for the province of Treviso accessible to local stakeholders and research institutions for risk assessments.

This report also serves as a basis for future studies. For example, drawing on the results of this study, the Conegliano Valdobbiadene Prosecco Wine Protection Consortium developed a set of considerations to propose mitigation and adaptation actions for viticulture in the Conegliano Valdobbiadene Prosecco area, while the University of Padua proposed an analysis of the relationship between climate change and grapevine diseases.

The document opens with a concise glossary that explains commonly used climate science terms in accessible language. The following chapters delve deeper into what climate change is, explain the rationale behind this initiative, and present the project's key findings and implications.

Glossary

ADAPTATION

In human systems, the process of adjustment to actual or expected climate and its effects, in order to moderate harm or exploit beneficial opportunities. In natural systems, the process of adjustment to actual climate and its effects; human intervention may facilitate adjustment to expected climate.

CLIMATE CHANGE

Significant changes in global temperatures and weather patterns over time. While natural factors can influence climate, recent changes are largely driven by human activities, particularly the burning of fossil fuels.

CLIMATE FORCING

Climate forcing refers to an external influence on the climate system that can cause changes in a range of climate variables. It is a factor that, when altered, can push the climate system toward warming or cooling. Examples include changes in solar radiation, volcanic eruptions that release large amounts of particulate matter into the atmosphere, and the increased concentration of greenhouse gases due to human activities. Positive forcing, such as increased greenhouse gas emissions, warms the Earth, while negative forcing, such as volcanic aerosols reflecting sunlight away from Earth, can lead to cooling.

CLIMATE INFORMATION

Climate information refers to data and knowledge about past, present, and future climate conditions and trends at regional scales. It is generated using various data sources and methodologies, including theoretical understanding, observed data from multiple datasets, simulations from different model types, attribution methodologies, and local knowledge. The information is then distilled through a co-production process involving users, stakeholders, and producers to ensure relevance, usefulness, and trust for decision-making. Climate change information at regional scales is essential for informing risk management and climate services.

CLIMATE MODEL

A complex computer simulation that represents the Earth's climate system. It uses mathematical equations to model the interactions between the atmosphere, oceans, land, and ice, allowing for the projection of future climate conditions.

DOWNSCALING

Downscaling refers to the set of techniques used to translate climate information produced by global or large-scale regional climate models into finer-scale (local or sub-regional) climate information that is more relevant for impact assessment, planning, and decision-making. Downscaling can be performed using dynamic methods (based on high-resolution regional climate models) or statistical methods (based on empirical relationships between climate variables at different scales). This process makes it possible to better represent local climate characteristics.

CLIMATE PROJECTIONS

Scientific estimates of future climate based on simulations by climate models.

CLIMATE SCENARIOS

Plausible representations of future climate based on past trends and assumptions about how human activities will evolve.

GLOBAL WARMING

The increase in Earth's average surface temperature.

GREENHOUSE EFFECT

A natural process in which certain gases present in the Earth's atmosphere, such as water vapor, carbon dioxide, methane, and nitrous oxide, trap heat from the sun, keeping the planet's surface warmer than it would be otherwise. This effect is fundamental to sustaining life on Earth by maintaining its climate within habitable ranges. Without the greenhouse effect, Earth's average surface temperature would be about 33°C (91°F) colder than the current average of approximately 15°C (59°F). However, human activities have significantly increased the concentrations of these greenhouse gases, enhancing the natural greenhouse effect and leading to global warming.

GREENHOUSE GASES (GHGS)

Gases that trap heat in the atmosphere, such as carbon dioxide, methane, and nitrous oxide.

MITIGATION

Actions taken to reduce or prevent the emission of greenhouse gases, aiming to curb the rate and magnitude of climate change. Examples include renewable energy adoption, energy efficiency measures, and carbon sequestration.

OBSERVATIONS

Historical data collected from meteorological stations and other monitoring systems.

REPRESENTATIVE CONCENTRATION PATHWAYS (RCPs)

Scenarios outlining different greenhouse gas concentration trajectories by the end of the 21st century. They range from very high (RCP 8.5, the most pessimistic) to very low (RCP 2.6, the most optimistic), depending on assumptions about economic development, technology, and policy.

CLIMATE RISKS

Climate risks refer to the potential for adverse consequences for human and natural systems resulting from climate change. Risks arise from the interaction between climate-related hazards and the exposure and vulnerability of human or natural systems, taking into account their adaptive capacity. When climate risks materialise, they result in impacts. The same climate-related hazard can therefore lead to very different outcomes depending on the level of exposure of a system, its vulnerability, and its capacity to adapt. The concept of risk is central to climate change assessment because it explains why climate change does not produce uniform effects, but instead generates highly differentiated impacts across regions, sectors, and populations.

01

Climate change: introduction

Provision of statistically downscaled climate change scenarios for risk assessment in the Trevigiano viticulture sector

1.1 Understanding what climate change is

Climate change and global warming represent one of the most pressing challenges for humanity in the 21st century. Driven primarily by the continued rise in greenhouse gas emissions from human activities, the Earth's climate system is experiencing rapid and unprecedented changes in modern history. Understanding these complex dynamics and their far-reaching impacts is essential for informed decision-making and effective action across all levels of society.

At the forefront of this global effort is the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC), established by the United Nations Environment Programme (*UNEP*) and the World Meteorological Organization (*WMO*). The IPCC is the leading international body for climate science, tasked with assessing the latest scientific knowledge on climate change through contributions from thousands of researchers worldwide. Through its rigorous peer-reviewed process, the IPCC produces comprehensive reports—such as the Assessment Reports (*ARs*), Special Reports, and Methodology Reports—that distill cutting-edge findings on the causes, impacts, and potential solutions to climate change. These reports serve as the foundation for climate policy, helping to guide international negotiations and inform the actions of governments, institutions, and civil society.

The most recent IPCC report, the Sixth Assessment Report (*AR6*, 2021), delivers stark conclusions. It confirms—unequivocally—that human influence is the dominant cause of global warming. The report documents alarming trends: rising global temperatures, accelerating sea-level rise, shrinking ice sheets and glaciers, and more frequent and intense extreme weather events. Crucially, *AR6* emphasizes the need for immediate, ambitious efforts to reduce emissions, adapt to unavoidable impacts, and foster international cooperation to limit warming and its consequences. One of the most common arguments used to downplay climate change is that the Earth was much warmer in the past, particularly during the early Holocene, and that life nonetheless thrived under those conditions. It is therefore claimed that the current warming of just under 1.5 °C above pre-industrial levels is not problematic in itself.

The fundamental flaw in this reasoning is that the challenge posed by climate change is not the absolute level of temperature, but the rate at which temperature is increasing. Ecosystems and species can adapt to changing climatic conditions when changes occur over long timescales, but they struggle to adapt when changes are extremely rapid. Past climatic shifts, including those during and after the last glacial period, unfolded over thousands to millions of years, allowing species to migrate, evolve, and reorganise gradually. In contrast, the current warming is occurring over mere decades. The present rate of global temperature increase is unprecedented in the context of human civilisation and likely exceeds the adaptive capacity of many species and ecosystems. As a result, climate change today represents not simply a warmer world, but a world changing too fast for biological, ecological, and social systems to adjust, leading to widespread disruption, increased extinction risk, and growing impacts on human societies.

1.2 Climate models and their purposes

A climate model is a numerical representation of the climate system based on the physical, chemical and biological properties of its components, its interactions and feedback processes.

More precisely, climate models are systems of differential equations based on the basic laws of physics, fluid motion and chemistry. To “run” a model, scientists divide the planet into a 3-dimensional grid formed by cells (Fig. 1), apply the basic equations, and also specify the climate forcing (for instance, setting variables to represent the amount of greenhouse gases in the atmosphere). The equations are solved in each cell (this requires large computational power). Results from each grid cell are passed to neighbouring cells, and the equations are solved again. Repeating the process through many time steps represents the passage of time. Climate models calculate winds, heat transfer, radiation, relative humidity, and surface hydrology within each grid and evaluate interactions with neighbouring points. Unlike models used for short-range weather forecasts, climate models do not attempt to predict what is going to happen at a specific place and point in time, i.e. they cannot produce a forecast for a specific date in the future. Instead, climate models are used to determine how the average and extreme conditions will change, for instance, if it will be warmer or cooler, wetter or drier, on average over the next e.g. 50 years.

Figure 1

Scheme of the three-dimensional grid of a global climate model and processes involved. Source: NOAA.

For this reason, climate studies usually consider 30-year periods to describe certain climatic conditions or to calculate the climate change signal (comparing the future with the present) for climate projections. Climate scenarios are plausible images of a future climate based on knowledge of the past climate and assumptions on its future change (to a great extent, related to the increase of greenhouse gas concentrations, Fig. 2). By constructing scenarios based on different assumptions, we can estimate the impact of climate change and quantify the inherently associated uncertainties. The Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change - Task Group on Data and Scenario Support for Impact and Climate Assessment (IPCC-TGICA) developed emission scenarios and translated them to Representative Concentration Pathways (RCP) using Integrated Assessment Models (IAMs). The RCPs were designed in such a way that they represent a wide range of radiative forcing of the climate system in 2100 and thus greenhouse gas (GHG) concentrations.

Figure 2

Emission scenarios and the resulting radiative forcing levels for the different Representative Concentration Pathways (RCPs, in different lines). Source: IPCC.

1.2 Climate models and their purposes

Describing the future climate, model and scenario uncertainty are important factors to be considered. Model uncertainty is the imperfect knowledge about the climate system, quantified through a large number of climate models that simulate the future climate for the same emission scenario. Thus it is recommended to use a combined product: a multi-model ensemble. It is important to give a range of possible future changes based on different scenarios and models, to account for the different levels of uncertainty. If signals emerge despite the different uncertainties, then robust messages can be extracted to provide useful climate information.

Despite the increasing spatial resolution (grid cells of about 100kmx100km nowadays) and complexity (more physical processes included) of global climate models (GCMs, which operate at a global scale), they still present systematic biases and are often too coarse to solve local processes. Therefore, to bridge the gap between global and local scales, different climate downscaling approaches have been developed since the 1990s, namely dynamical and statistical downscaling. While dynamical downscaling solves the numerical equations of the climate system in a smaller domain (e.g., a continent) at a higher resolution based on regional climate models, statistical downscaling establishes an empirical/statistical relationship between large-scale variables from the climate model and local variables (e.g. surface temperature/precipitation at a target location, Fig. 3). Examples of large-scale variables (predictors) are sea level pressure and temperature, humidity and winds at different heights of the atmosphere, which are taken over a large enough spatial extent around the target point or grid cell. Predictors are usually well-represented by climate models and should have a significant and physically interpretable association with the predictand (Wilby et al. 2014).

Typically used statistical methods are analogues and regression models. The former is based on the local occurrences corresponding to a set of historical analogues of the predictor fields (i.e. similar synoptic situations).

The latter consists of transfer functions based on linear (e.g. multiple linear regression and generalized linear models) or non-linear (e.g. neural networks) regression models to infer the relationships between the large-scale predictors and the local predictand. An evaluation of different predictor variables, different domains for the predictors and different statistical methods using observations is required to select the best configuration prior to the application of the downscaling to future scenarios (Gutiérrez et al. 2013, 2019; San Martín et al. 2017; Maraun et al. 2019).

Figure 3

Scheme of the statistical downscaling process. Z, T, Q represent geopotential height, air temperature and specific humidity, respectively, at different pressure (vertical) levels in the atmosphere. Source: ENSEMBLES statistical downscaling portal.

1.3 Importance of climate information in adaptation planning

Climate information refers to data and knowledge about past, present, and future climate conditions and trends.

It can be broadly categorized based on the time scale:

- Short-to-medium-term climate information includes weather forecasts (short range for a few days, medium range up to one week and extended range up to six weeks) and seasonal outlooks.
- Long-term climate information provides insights into climate monitoring, trends and future risks, often over decades, and is essential for strategic planning and decision-making.

Long-term climate information is especially critical for climate change adaptation, as it supports the development of measures to increase resilience in human communities and natural ecosystems.

This information plays a central role in adaptation planning by enabling stakeholders to:

1. Identify vulnerabilities

Climate data helps pinpoint regions, sectors, and populations that are most at risk from climate-related hazards, such as extreme heat, sea-level rise, or shifts in rainfall patterns. This knowledge enables targeted interventions and prioritization of resources.

2. Anticipate future risks

Climate projections allow decision-makers to anticipate how risks may evolve under different greenhouse gas emission scenarios. For example, projections of declining rainfall can support the development of water management strategies, while projections of sea-level rise may prompt the reinforcement of coastal defenses.

3. Inform decision-making

Infrastructure design, urban planning, agriculture, and public health all benefit from considering future climate scenarios. For instance, cities might invest in flood-resilient transport systems or design buildings better suited to hotter climates.

4. Support risk assessments

Robust climate data enables comprehensive risk assessments by quantifying the likelihood and potential consequences of climate hazards. This helps governments and organizations prioritize adaptation actions and allocate resources effectively.

5. Build trust and foster engagement

Transparent, accessible climate information can enhance trust among stakeholders and communities. It encourages informed participation, supports dialogue, and facilitates collaboration in the development of locally relevant adaptation strategies.

1.4 Project overview

All the above points out the fundamental role of climate information for effective adaptation planning.

The rationale behind this is easy to understand: knowledge of future climatic conditions enables us to make informed investments. For instance, projections indicating a steady decline in average rainfall over the next few decades can prompt investments in drought-resilient crops or improved water management systems. Such long-term insights are essential for strategic adaptation planning, allowing communities and decision-makers to invest wisely in building resilience to climate risks. Despite the apparent value of these services and the information they convey, forecasting the future, especially over longer periods, presents challenges in both complexity and reliability. As discussed earlier, climate models are pivotal in providing this kind of prediction.

To ensure that climate projections are as relevant and accurate as possible for specific locations, various approaches and techniques are employed. Among these, one of the most effective approaches involves leveraging historical observed data to make climate model outputs more useful (i.e. less biased and with a higher spatial resolution) through statistical downscaling. However, the application of this approach on a global scale is hampered by the availability of reliable historical observed records, which ideally should span at least 20-30 years—a limitation in many parts of the world where observations are scarce. Fortunately, for the Veneto region, the Regional Agency for Environmental Prevention and Protection (ARPAV) and CondifesaTVB facilitated access to essential historical observed data across numerous locations. This has enabled the “customisation” of climate models for the province of Treviso. Building on the provision of downscaled future climate scenarios through statistical downscaling, it is possible to derive specific climate indicators crucial for targeted sectors-

viticulture being our primary focus. The selected climate indicators are vital as they enable us to understand how changes in climate variables, such as temperature and precipitation, could influence grape cultivation and overall the industry’s sustainability.

Therefore, as outlined in the preface of this document, this project aimed at providing long-term climate information for several locations in Treviso and tailored to a specific sector, viticulture, for supporting risk assessments. The availability of historical meteorological records and their usage for the downscaling methodology made this work technically solid and unique. The climate projections generated in this study consist of daily temperature, precipitation and relative humidity values for several locations in Treviso, for various climate models and scenarios through the end of the century, which can be used for various downstream analyses. The quality assessment of the statistical downscaling methodology focused specifically on viticulture-related climate indicators.

Therefore, while the generated climate projections can support diverse applications such as hydrological and epidemiological modeling, we cannot guarantee its quality for purposes outside the viticulture sector.

Present climate and climate hazards relevant to viticulture

Provision of statistically downscaled climate change scenarios for risk assessment in the Trevigiano viticulture sector

2.1 Observed climate

To study the past climate in the province of Treviso we consider a set of 24 meteorological stations with daily measurements of temperature, precipitation and relative humidity data since at least 1991 (see Annex 1 for more details).

We selected 1991-2020 as the baseline period for our analyses i) to maximize overlap with other datasets needed for downscaling, ii) to have a long enough dataset to train the downscaling methods (30 years) and iii) to assemble as many stations as possible. The meteorological stations used in this study are shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4

All monitoring stations included in the study are mapped (ARPAV in orange; CondifesaTVB in red). A smaller subset of stations-chosen for the hill-vs-plain comparative analyses-is highlighted with tree icons (hill sites) and leaf icons (flat sites).

2.1/1 General overview

The climate in the province of Treviso has changed in the last 30 years, particularly concerning temperatures. According to our analyses, both mean, maximum and minimum daily temperatures have been increasing at a rate of 0.04-0.12°C/year (depending upon station), being about half a degree per decade for half of the stations. Following this logic, it means that a person born in 1992 in, for instance, Villorba could have experienced, on average, a mean annual temperature up to 1.5 °C lower than a person born in 2021. The stations that recorded the strongest increase in annual mean of daily mean temperatures have been the ones of Farra di Soligo and Volpago del Montello. In general, we detected a consistent and statistically relevant increase in annual mean of daily mean, maximum and minimum temperature for all analysed stations. We have also found statistically significant changes in cumulative annual rainfall, particularly for stations located in hill areas, like Vittorio Veneto. Relative humidity appears to be decreasing at a rate of 1% per year in stations like Conegliano and Tezze.

These local findings are echoed by the broader spatial patterns summarized in Table 1, which shows the average climate conditions for representative hill and flat stations during 1991-2020. Flat areas showed higher daily maximum temperature values, potentially reflecting more intense warming during the hottest periods. Hill stations also received notably more annual rainfall (1335.9 mm vs. 1073.9 mm), while relative humidity was consistently lower in hill areas (71.2%) than in the plains (79%), aligning with the observed decreasing trends in humidity at stations such as Conegliano and Tezze.

Together, these results confirm that the observed climate changes are not only station-specific but also exhibit consistent geographic patterns-particularly with warming affecting both hill and flat areas, and humidity declining in all representative stations. The colour coding in Table 1 further underlines the statistical robustness of these trends, with most variables showing consistent and significant changes across the selected stations.

2.1/1 General overview

	Hill	Flat
Daily mean temperature (T _{mean} , °C)	13,6	13,2
Daily maximum temperature (T _{max} , °C)	18,0	18,8
Daily minimum temperature (T _{min} , °C)	9,8	8,3
Annual accumulated precipitation (Pr, mm/yr)	1335,9	1073,9
Daily mean relative humidity (Rel. Hum., %)	71,2	79

Table 1

Summary for the five meteorological variables considered over 1991-2020. Numbers represent the mean over selected hill and flat stations (Valdobbiadene-Bigolino, Farra di Soligo, Vittorio Veneto and Conegliano are representatives of hill stations and Villorba, Vazzola-Tezze, Gaiarine, Zero Branco, Roncade and Oderzo are representatives of flat stations).

Colours represent trends significance (red if all selected stations present statistically significant trends, orange if all stations but one present statistically significant trends, black if less stations present statistically significant trends). Note that increasing trends are found for the three temperatures and decreasing for relative humidity (see Figs. 5-9).

2.1/2 Technical summary

Table 2 summarizes the mean values (and their variability) for the meteorological variables of interest for the period 1991-2020 for a subset of stations, which are located either in hills or plain areas. These stations will be considered for more detailed analyses in subsequent sections.

	Valdobbiadene Bigolino	Farra di Soligo	Vittorio Veneto	Conegliano	Villorba	Vazzola Tezze	Gaiarine	Zero Branco	Roncade	Oderzo
	225 m a.s.l.	169 m a.s.l.	123 m a.s.l.	90 m a.s.l.	41 m a.s.l.	40 m a.s.l.	17 m a.s.l.	12 m a.s.l.	7 m a.s.l.	7 m a.s.l.
T _{mean} °C	13,2 (0,6)	13,2 (0,5)	13,9 (0,7)	14,5 (1,0)	13,0 (0,7)	13,3 (0,6)	13,4 (0,6)	13,3 (0,7)	13,2 (0,7)	13,1 (0,6)
T _{max} °C	17,4 (0,6)	18,1 (0,6)	18,5 (0,8)	18,4 (1,1)	18,8 (0,7)	18,7 (0,6)	19,1 (0,7)	18,8 (0,6)	18,7 (0,7)	18,7 (0,7)
T _{min} °C	9,7 (0,6)	8,9 (0,6)	10,0 (0,7)	10,9 (0,9)	8,0 (0,8)	8,3 (0,8)	8,2 (0,6)	8,6 (0,9)	8,5 (0,9)	8,1 (0,7)
Pr mm/ yr	1406,4 (431,3)	1458,7 (452,7)	1049,0 (745,9)	1216,3 (296,1)	1050,1 (315,7)	1129,8 (345,6)	1169,0 (370,7)	910,9 (299,5)	985,7 (314,9)	946,8 (315,7)
Rel. Hum. %	71,5 (3,9)	74,6 (3,3)	70,4 (4,5)	68,6 (4,1)	79,0 (3,2)	78,5 (3,5)	78,6 (3,2)	79,1 (3,1)	79,7 (2,7)	79,6 (2,6)

Table 2

Summary for the five meteorological variables and 10 exemplary stations considered. Valdobbiadene-Bigolino, Farra di Soligo, Vittorio Veneto and Conegliano are representatives of hill stations and Villorba, Vazzola-Tezze, Gaiarine, Zero Branco, Roncade and Oderzo are representatives of flat stations (elevation above sea level is indicated together with the station name). Numbers represent the mean value and the standard deviation (in brackets) in the period 1991-2020 for each variable and station.

2.1/2 Technical summary

Figures 5-9 show the overall climate conditions in 1991-2020 in the region, i.e. annual mean values of daily mean, maximum and minimum temperatures and relative humidity and annual accumulated precipitation. Daily mean, maximum and minimum temperatures range across most stations (90% of them) between 12-14.5°C, 17-19°C, 8-11°C (Figs. 5, 6 and 7, upper left panels), respectively, except for Monte Cesen where values are significantly lower. Increasing observed trends of daily mean and minimum temperature are evident in most stations (Figs. 5 and 7). Trends of maximum temperature are statistically significant in fewer stations, but up to 0.1°C/year in Volpago del Montello, Valdobbiadene - Bigolino and other low-lying stations (Fig. 6). The negative trend in Follina Antincendio (of about 0.15°C) may be due to changes in the meteorological station setup, thus it should not be considered.

Figure 5

Annual mean values of daily mean temperature in 1991-2020 (upper left panel) and their trends in the same period (upper right panel). Trends are the slopes of the linear model fitted with the interannual time series; empty circles mean non-statistically significant trends for a confidence level of 95%. (Lower panel) Temporal evolution of annual mean temperature in 1993-2020. Lines depict the average of four stations located in hills (green line; corresponding to: Valdobbiadene - Bigolino, Farra di Soligo, Vittorio Veneto and Conegliano) and six stations located in flat areas (orange line; corresponding to: Villorba, Vazzola - Tezze, Gaiarine, Zero Branco, Roncade and Oderzo). The averaged 30-year time series was smoothed using a 5-year moving window. See Table 2 for more details on the selected stations.

Figure 6

As Fig. 5 but for daily maximum temperature.

Figure 7

As Fig.5 but for daily minimum temperature.

2.1/2 Technical summary

Annual accumulated precipitation shows a clear orographic pattern with the highest amounts accumulated closer to the Alps and hills (Fig. 8). Overall, precipitation increased from the 1990s to the 2010s and decreased in the last decade. Relative humidity is highest in the locations closer to the Adriatic Sea and in Monte Cesen (Fig. 9). It showed a decreasing trend, especially accentuated from the 1990s to the 2010s, although it is statistically significant only in a few stations such as Conegliano, Villorba, Vazzola - Tezze and Gaiarine.

Figure 8

 As Fig.5 but for annual accumulated precipitation in mm.

Figure 9

 As Fig.5 but for relative humidity in %.

2.2 Current climate hazards relevant to viticulture

Climate indexes important for viticulture were identified in consultation with the **Consorzio di Tutela del Vino Conegliano Valdobbiadene Prosecco**. These indicators are listed in Table 4 and were calculated considering the grapes growing season (April to September).

2.2/1 General overview

Between April and September, mean temperatures have increased across both hill and flat stations. In the early 1990s, the average daily temperature for this period was around 1.5 °C lower than in 2020s in most stations.

However, among all temperature-related indices, only the increase in warm nights is statistically significant (highlighted in color in Table 3). These nighttime warming trends are particularly pronounced in hill areas, where stations recorded an average of 50.1 days with minimum temperatures above 18 °C and 23.4 days above 20 °C. Flat stations showed significantly fewer such nights-32.6 and 10.0 days, respectively. The statistical significance of these trends (coloured values) suggests a robust shift toward warmer nights, which can influence grape ripening, acidity, and disease dynamics.

In contrast, while the number of hot days and heatwaves appears higher in flat areas-particularly the number of days with maximum temperature above 30°C, with 41.4 days compared to 28.1 in hill areas-trends are not statistically significant. Similarly, the average number of heatwave events remains relatively low across both zones, suggesting that increases in daily extremes have not yet translated into longer-lasting heat events.

Rainfall is consistently higher in hill stations across all growing season months, with notable differences in May (146.2 mm in hills vs. 111.0 mm in flats) and August (137.2 mm vs. 89.9 mm). Hill areas also experience more wet days (daily precipitation above 5mm) and slightly shorter dry spells, but these differences, while potentially relevant agronomically, are not statistically significant.

A key finding is the statistically significant decrease in the number of days with high relative humidity (above 85%) at a rate of about 4-8 days per decade. This decreasing trend points to drier atmospheric conditions, which may reduce disease risk but increase irrigation needs and hydric stress during critical vine growth phases.

Table 3 provides a summary of these findings, showing that while multiple variables suggest a warming and changing climate during the grape growing season, only night-time temperatures and relative humidity (in flat areas) show robust, statistically significant trends.

These indicators are especially relevant for viticultural planning and adaptation in the Veneto region.

2.2/1 General overview

	Hill	Flat
Daily mean temperature (°C)	19,6	19,5
Number of days with Tmax > 30°C (days)	28,1	41,4
Number of days with Tmax > 35°C (days)	1,5	3,8
Number of events with at least 5 days with Tmax > 30 (# HWs)	2,2	3,0
Number of events with at least 3 days with Tmax > 35 (# HWs)	0,5	0,7
Number of nights with Tmin > 18°C (days)	50,1	32,6
Number of nights with Tmin > 20°C (days)	23,4	10,0
Number of days with Precip > 5mm (days)	36,6	29,6
Mean number of consecutive days with Precip <1mm (days)	4,2	4,8
Precipitation sum for April (mm)	123,6	93,0
Precipitation sum for May (mm)	146,2	111,0
Precipitation sum for June (mm)	131,0	96,8
Precipitation sum for July (mm)	109,3	81,8
Precipitation sum for August (mm)	137,2	89,9
Precipitation sum for September (mm)	135,2	114,6
Number of days with relative humidity > 85% (days)	21,3	31,3

Table 3

As Table 1, but for climate indices in April-September. In this case increasing trends (coloured numbers) are found for the temperature-related indices and decreasing trends for the number of days with relative humidity > 85%.

2.2/2 Technical summary

This section shows observed values for a set of climate hazards relevant to viticulture (Table 4). For this purpose, only the months from April to September are considered. Averaged conditions alongside their variation for the 10 selected stations are shown in Table 5.

Index	Variable	Description
Tmean	Daily mean temperature	Daily mean temperature (Apr-Sep)
TX30	Daily maximum temperature	Number of days (Apr-Sep) with Tmax > 30°C
TX35	Daily maximum temperature	Number of days (Apr-Sep) with Tmax > 35°C
HW30	Daily maximum temperature	Number of events (Apr-Sep) with at least 5 consecutive days with Tmax > 30
HW35	Daily maximum temperature	Number of events (Apr-Sep) with at least 3 consecutive days with Tmax > 35
TN18	Daily minimum temperature	Number of days (Apr-Sep) with Tmin > 18°C
TN20	Daily minimum temperature	Number of days (Apr-Sep) with Tmin > 20°C
PR5	Daily accumulated precipitation	Number of days (Apr-Sep) with Precip > 5mm
CDD	Daily accumulated precipitation	Mean number of consecutive days with Precip <1mm (Apr-Sep)
PrAccX	Daily accumulated precipitation	Precipitation sum for month X
HU85	Daily mean relative humidity	Number of days (Apr-Sep) with Rel.Hum. > 85%

Table 4

Climate indices representing climate hazards relevant to viticulture.

	Valdobbiadene Bigolino	Farra di Soligo	Vittorio Veneto	Conegliano	Villorba	Vazzola Tezze	Gaiarine	Zero Branco	Roncade	Oderzo
	225 m a.s.l.	169 m a.s.l.	123 m a.s.l.	90 m a.s.l.	41 m a.s.l.	40 m a.s.l.	17 m a.s.l.	12 m a.s.l.	7 m a.s.l.	7 m a.s.l.
Tmean °C	19,1 (0,8)	19,1 (0,7)	19,9 (0,8)	20,2 (0,9)	19,3 (0,8)	19,5 (0,7)	19,8 (0,8)	19,6 (0,8)	19,3 (0,8)	19,5 (0,9)
TX30 days	20,8 (10,5)	27,6 (11,3)	33,3 (14,1)	31,0 (14,6)	43,5 (14,3)	37,6 (11,5)	43,7 (15,2)	43,2 (15,8)	38,1 (13,9)	41,6 (14,2)
TX35 days	0,6 (1,6)	1,2 (1,9)	2,4 (3,4)	2,0 (3,2)	4,3 (5,2)	2,4 (2,9)	4,5 (4,8)	4,5 (4,5)	3,1 (3,6)	3,6 (4,9)
HW30 # HWs	1,7 (1,1)	2,2 (1,2)	2,6 (1,3)	2,3 (1,3)	3,1 (1,3)	2,9 (1,2)	3,2 (1,2)	3,0 (1,5)	2,8 (1,2)	3,0 (1,2)
HW35 # HWs	0,3 (0,5)	0,4 (0,5)	0,4 (0,5)	0,7 (0,8)	0,7 (0,9)	0,4 (0,7)	0,8 (1,0)	0,8 (0,8)	0,7 (0,7)	0,5 (0,7)
TN18 days	48,3 (15,7)	32,0 (12,8)	54,8 (14,6)	63,7 (15,0)	30,5 (14,9)	29,9 (13,9)	31,9 (12,9)	35,8 (17,9)	28,2 (14,0)	36,5 (18,6)
TN20 days	21,2 (11,3)	10,4 (7,6)	26,3 (10,9)	34,7 (14,0)	8,9 (7,8)	8,5 (7,2)	9,7 (7,6)	11,3 (9,0)	7,5 (6,4)	12,7 (11,0)
PR5 days	36,8 (6,9)	37,9 (6,7)	37,6 (6,6)	33,2 (6,4)	30,2 (5,4)	31,9 (6,5)	32,5 (6,2)	27,1 (6,5)	26,2 (6,9)	28,6 (6,2)
CDD days	4,1 (0,6)	4,2 (0,5)	4,0 (0,6)	4,4 (0,5)	4,7 (0,8)	4,6 (0,7)	4,4 (0,6)	5,2 (0,7)	5,1 (0,7)	4,8 (0,8)
Pr Apr mm	128,8 (74,6)	130,7 (83,9)	124,8 (86,0)	104,7 (60,8)	96,3 (56,2)	98,1 (53,4)	102,8 (61,2)	82,4 (44,5)	83,9 (48,5)	90,2 (53,3)
Pr Mag mm	149,9 (83,7)	153,1 (96,1)	145,5 (71,1)	128,1 (78,7)	111,7 (65,8)	115,2 (68,3)	117,8 (68,6)	94,1 (65,6)	100,7 (69,4)	110,5 (66,2)
Pr Giu mm	137,3 (70,6)	136,0 (69,5)	137,2 (73,1)	115,3 (57,6)	98,2 (49,1)	110,3 (53,5)	102,0 (51,9)	91,5 (53,3)	86,9 (41,1)	91,2 (49,6)
Pr Lug mm	137,3 (70,6)	136,0 (69,5)	137,2 (73,1)	115,3 (57,6)	98,2 (49,1)	110,3 (53,5)	102,0 (51,9)	91,5 (53,3)	86,9 (41,1)	91,2 (49,6)
Pr Ago mm	126,1 (71,6)	145,8 (84,2)	153,3 (80,5)	113,5 (66,0)	87,9 (45,7)	100,6 (65,5)	105,1 (58,0)	77,1 (42,5)	80,1 (45,0)	82,0 (50,2)
Pr Set mm	126,8 (56,5)	152,2 (58,1)	139,7 (60,7)	120,0 (61,0)	115,8 (56,5)	128,6 (61,3)	123,3 (59,2)	96,0 (47,0)	107,0 (58,9)	109,0 (51,2)
HU85 days	23,7 (11,5)	26,4 (12,7)	17,3 (14,1)	18,4 (11,4)	31,9 (17,4)	34,0 (16,1)	30,5 (13,0)	30,1 (16,9)	30,9 (14,0)	33,2 (14,9)

Table 5

As Table 2 but for the relevant indices for viticulture, for April-September.

	Valdobbiadene Bigolino	Farra di Soligo	Vittorio Veneto	Conegliano	Villorba	Vazzola Tezze	Gaiarine	Zero Branco	Roncade	Oderzo
	225 m a.s.l.	169 m a.s.l.	123 m a.s.l.	90 m a.s.l.	41 m a.s.l.	40 m a.s.l.	17 m a.s.l.	12 m a.s.l.	7 m a.s.l.	7 m a.s.l.
HW30 # HWs	49	63	54	70	89	85	94	86	82	88
HW35 # HWs	2	5	5	10	16	9	18	20	14	12

Table 6

Total number of heat waves in 1991-2020 in the 10 illustrative selected stations.

2.2/2 Technical summary

Temperature-Related Indices (Figs. 10–15)

- Tmean (April–September) has increased in nearly all stations, with trends that are statistically significant for most of them. Hills and plains show similar upward tendencies, but plain stations typically present slightly higher absolute temperatures.
- Hot extremes (TX30, TX35, Heat Waves) generally occur more often in plain areas, although only few trends are statistically significant. Particularly, Villorba, Gaiarine, and Zero Branco exhibit a significant increase in the number of HW30 events (heat waves of more than 5 consecutive days with maximum temperature > 30 °C). Meanwhile, HW35 (heat waves of more than 3 consecutive days with maximum temperature >35 °C) is rare across the region, typically happening, on average, less than once per year.
- Warm nights (TN18, TN20) show a consistent upward trend in most stations. On average, TN18 increases by about 1 day per year, while TN20 increases by approximately 1 day every two years. Interestingly, hill stations such as Valdobbiadene-Bigolino and Conegliano record a larger number of these warm nights compared to many plain stations, suggesting nighttime conditions in elevated areas are also becoming warmer.

Figure 10

 As Fig. 5
 but for Tmean in
 April-September.

Figure 11

 As Fig. 5
 but for TX30 in
 April-September.

Figure 12
 As Fig. 5 but for TX35 in April-September.

Figure 14
 As Fig. 5 but for TN18 in April-September.

Figure 13
 As Fig. 5 but for HW30 in April-September (see Table 6 for more details).

Figure 15
 As Fig. 5 but for TN20 in April-September.

2.2/2 Technical summary

Precipitation (Fig. 16-18)

- The number of days with accumulations above 5 mm (PR5) is generally higher in hilly or mountainous stations, likely reflecting orographic effects. Conversely, consecutive dry days (CDD) are typically more prolonged in the plains; for instance, Zero Branco experiences around 5 consecutive dry days on average. Neither PR5 nor CDD shows a statistically significant trend over the study period.
- Across all stations, May and September stand out as the months with the largest precipitation totals during the growing season. A clear orographic pattern persists throughout the year, with hilly stations receiving more rainfall overall.
- Some stations - Farra di Soligo, Villorba, Gaiarine, Zero Branco, and Roncade - show increasing May precipitation trends, which are significant in a few cases (see coloured markers in Fig. 18).

Figure 16

Annual mean values of PR5 (upper left panel) and CDD in April-September in 1991-2020 (upper right panel) and their temporal evolution (middle panel for PR5 and lower panel for CDD). Trends for these indicators are not statistically significant at any station.

Figure 17
 Monthly accumulated precipitation in April-September in 1991-2020. Trends are only statistically significant, for some stations, in May (see Fig. 18).

Figure 18
 Trends (upper panel) and temporal evolution of monthly accumulated precipitation (bottom panel) in May (1991-2020).

Relative Humidity (Fig. 19)

- The number of days with mean relative humidity above 85% (HU85) falls, on average, between 20 and 40 days (April-September) in most stations. Locations like Monte Cesen and Ogliono (and some near the coast) tend to exhibit the highest HU85 values.
- A significant decreasing trend in HU85 emerges at several stations, including Farra di Soligo, Conegliano, Villorba, Vazzola-Tezze, Gaiarine, Zero Branco, Roncade, and Oderzo. This suggests progressively drier air conditions in many parts of Veneto, which could have implications for both vine disease risk and irrigation needs.

Figure 19
 As Fig. 5 but for HU85 in April-September.

2.3 Evaluation of the downscaling methodology

The data recorded by ARPAV and Condifesa meteorological stations was used to “tailor” future climate data available from climate model outputs to the reality of the province of Treviso and the indicators important for viticulture.

This is done through different statistical techniques that are summarised in Annex 2. As explained in the introduction chapter, statistical downscaling was used to generate future daily climate data up to the end of the century and according to two different climate scenarios, which are based on how much greenhouse gases humanity will introduce into the atmosphere. These daily climate data can be used to run impact models, such as epidemiological models (for modelling grape diseases).

2.3/1 Technical summary

An exhaustive evaluation of different statistical downscaling methods using different predictor sets has been carried out. In particular, all methods and predictor configurations have been tested focusing specifically on the climate indices relevant to viticulture (Table 4). Results for the selected predictor sets are shown in Figure 20. Overall, small biases are found for daily mean and maximum temperature indices, whereas worse performances are found for indices related to daily minimum temperature. Relatively small biases are found for accumulated precipitation (most of them below 10%) and HU85 (less than 5 days). More details about the spatial distribution of biases in the cross-validation experiment and the rationale behind the use of linear regression instead of analogs methods for temperatures can be found in Annex 2.

Figure 20

Overall evaluation of the downscaling methods and selected predictor set in the cross-validation experiment. Each cell represents the bias (mean deviation of the predicted values, with respect to the observed ones, expressed in relative terms in the lower panel) for each climate hazard (rows) and station (in columns). Biases for Tmean in °C; for TX30, TX35, TN18, TN20, CDD and PR5 in days; for HW30 and HW35 in number of heat waves and for monthly accumulated precipitation (for the different months analyzed, lower panel) in percentage.

Future climate and climate hazards relevant to viticulture

Provision of statistically downscaled climate change scenarios for risk assessment in the Trevigiano viticulture sector

3.1 Future climate projections

Through the application of the statistical downscaling methodology, we generated daily future projections of minimum temperature, maximum temperature, mean temperature, accumulated precipitation and relative humidity up to the end of the century for six global climate models and two emission scenarios.

3.1/1 General overview

Our downscaled projections indicate that, by the end of the century, the province of Treviso could see substantial increases in annual mean daily maximum, mean, and minimum temperatures, ranging from 1 °C to 4 °C (depending upon station) above the climatological values corresponding to the 1991-2020 baseline period. As summarized in Table 7, these temperature increases are robust across all models and stations (shown in red), underscoring high confidence in a warmer future. Under moderate emissions, mean temperature (T_{mean}) could rise by roughly +1.7 °C in hilly areas and +3.6 °C in flatter zones, while under strong emissions, this variable is projected to increase by +3.6 °C in both regions. Similarly, daily maximum (T_{max}) and minimum (T_{min}) temperatures show consistent warming signals, reaching up to +4.1 °C for T_{max} in flat areas under both scenarios.

By contrast, the climate change signal found for precipitation under moderate emission, which is projected to decrease by -3.2% in hills and by -11.6% in flat, does not exhibit uniformly high model agreement (thus it is not coded red in Table 7). Under the strong emissions scenario, however, models agree on a larger and more robust decrease of approximately -13.5% in hill zones and -11.6% in flat areas. A similar pattern of partial uncertainty applies to relative humidity, which shows a modest change (-0.6% in hills, +0.9% in flats) under moderate emissions and more pronounced decreases under stronger warming (-1.2% in hills, -0.9% in flats) - but again, not all models agree to the same extent.

As a whole, these findings consistently point to a warmer and drier climate in the province of Treviso by the late 21st century, with temperatures confidently expected to rise across both hills and plains. Although the sign of precipitation and humidity changes is predominantly negative, especially under stronger emission, model agreement is smaller in the moderate emissions scenario. Even so, a future marked by high temperatures and reduced water availability remains the central projection, reinforcing the need for climate adaptation measures in agriculture, water management, and regional planning.

It is important to note that an increase in the mean temperature, such as the 1°C of global warming often discussed in climate science, tells us little about how variability or extreme events may change, i.e. changes might be larger (leading to more extreme conditions) in individual years due to year-to-year variability. To illustrate, consider two different 3-year mean temperature sequences, each with the same average (mean) temperature. In the first sequence, temperatures are relatively stable (e.g., 15°C, 18°C, 23°C; mean = 19°C). In a second, more variable scenario, temperatures might be 10°C, 16°C, and 31°, again averaging 19°C. Both periods have the same mean, but the second has much greater variability and includes a much higher extreme.

In the climate change context, it is typical to report changes in multi-decade (e.g., 30-year) means. However, it is important to recognize that increases in these long-term averages may arise from a wide range of possible changes in year-to-year variability and extremes. In other words, the same increase in mean temperature could mask very different patterns of extreme heat events, which are often more relevant to impacts than the mean alone.

3.1/1 General overview

	Moderate emissions scenario		Strong emissions scenario	
	Hill	Flat	Hill	Flat
Daily mean temperature (Tmean, °C)	1,7	3,6	3,6	3,6
Daily maximum temperature (Tmax, °C)	1,9	4,1	4,0	4,1
Daily minimum temperature (Tmin, °C)	1,5	3,0	3,2	3,0
Annual accumulated precipitation (Pr, %)	-3,2	-11,6	-13,5	-11,6
Daily mean relative humidity (Rel. Hum., %)	-0,6	0,9	-1,2	-0,9

Table 7

Summary of the projected changes for the five meteorological variables considered over 2071-2100, with respect to 1990-2020, for two different emission scenarios (moderate and strong).

Numbers represent the climate change signals (mean of all climate models) over selected hill and flat stations, respectively (Valdobbiadene-Bigolino, Farra di Soligo, Vittorio Veneto and Conegliano are representatives of hill stations and Villorba, Vazzola-Tezze, Gaiarine, Zero Branco, Roncade and Oderzo are representatives of flat stations). These signals are calculated as future minus present climate, except for precipitation which is calculated as a relative change.

Colours represent signals robustness (red if signals in all climate models have the same sign in all selected stations, orange if signals in all climate models have the same sign in all stations but one, black if signals have conflicting signs across climate models or across stations). Note that increasing changes are found for the three temperatures and decreasing ones for precipitation and relative humidity.

3.1/2 Technical summary

Once the statistical downscaling methods have been trained and tested in perfect conditions (Sec. 4.3), the best configuration found is used to project the local future climate, using predictors from Global Climate Models (GCMs). We consider six GCMs (Table 8) under two emission scenarios developed by the IPCC, namely RCP 4.5 (moderate emissions) and RCP 8.5 (strong emissions). These GCMs were interpolated from their different native spatial resolutions to a common 2x2° grid (as ERA5, see Annex 2) and pre-processed to make them compatible with ERA5 by applying a monthly bias correction strategy which allows for harmonizing their annual cycles. The ability of the chosen GCMs to reproduce large-scale dynamics has already been assessed in previous studies (Brands et al., 2013, Baño-Medina et al. 2022).

GCM name	Institution	Spatial Res.
CanESM2 (Christian et al., 2010)	Canadian Centre for Climate Modelling and Analysis	(2,81°, 2,79°)
CNRM-CM5 (Voltaire et al., 2013)	Centre National de Recherches Météorologiques and Centre Européen de Recherche et de Formation Avancée	(1,4°, 1,4°)
MPI-ESM-MR (Müller et al., 2018)	Max-Planck-Institut für Meteorologie	(1,87°, 1,87°)
MPI-ESM-LR (Müller et al., 2018)	Max-Planck-Institut für Meteorologie	(1,87°, 1,87°)
NorESM1-M (Bentsen et al., 2013)	Norwegian Climate Center	(2,5°, 1,9°)
GFDL-ESM2M (Dunne et al., 2013)	National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration Geophysical Fluid Dynamics Laboratory	(2,5°, 2,02°)

Table 8

List of global climate models used in this work. Note that, for the region under study, 1° corresponds to approximately a 100km x 100km box.

3.1/2 Technical summary

Results show that mean, maximum and minimum temperatures are projected to increase by the end of the century homogeneously across stations (Fig. 21). Under a moderate emission scenario, they might increase around 1°C, whereas the increment is about 3.5-4°C for mean temperature under strong emissions. Interestingly, the increase in maximum temperature (about 4-5°C) is larger than minimum (around 2-3°C).

Figure 21

Climate change signals for daily mean temperature (first row), daily maximum temperature (second row) and daily minimum temperature (third row) in °C.

This signal is calculated as the mean difference between the period 2071-2100 and 1990-2020, under two emission scenarios (columns). Values correspond to the multi-model ensemble mean (the mean of the six climate models considered).

Total annual precipitation is projected to reduce by around 15% under the strongest emission scenario while non-relevant changes are expected under moderate emissions (Fig. 22, upper panel). Very small changes are projected for daily mean relative humidity (below 2% reductions under the strong emission scenario, Fig. 22 lower panel).

Figure 22

As Fig. 21, but for annual accumulated precipitation (first row, expressed in relative terms, i.e., as a percentage) and relative humidity (second row).

3.2 Future climate hazards relevant to viticulture

3.2/1 General overview

According to the downscaled projections (Table 9), Veneto's grape-growing season will likely become noticeably warmer by the end of the century, even under moderate-emissions, compared to 1990-2020. In particular, mean daily temperature (T_{mean}) during April–September could rise by about +1.8 to +1.9 °C in hills and plains, respectively, and by as much as +4.2 °C under a stronger-emissions pathway. Moreover, the number of days exceeding 30 °C (TX30) are projected to nearly double in the moderate scenario (around 28–31 additional days), and could even triple, increasing roughly 60 days, in the stronger one. Similarly, the number of days above 35 °C (TX35) is also projected to increase up to 30-40 additional days in a high-emissions scenario. Consequently, heatwaves (HW30, HW35) become more frequent, with a significant increment in five-day events above 30 °C (HW30), especially in hilly areas under stronger emissions, and multi-day episodes above 35 °C (HW35) remaining rare but increasing substantially from present levels.

The number of warm nights (TN18, TN20) exhibits robust upward increments in both scenarios, roughly doubling or even tripling compared to the values found for the baseline period.

In contrast, precipitation-related indices mostly decline, particularly in the peak of summer (July and August). The frequency of rainfall events above 5 mm (PR5) decreases by 4 to 8 days (depending upon scenario), while consecutive dry spells (CDD) lengthen by up to 1.4 days under strong emissions. Certain months, such as July and August, show a robust decline of accumulated precipitation (as large as -50%) across most models and stations in the stronger scenario, whereas the moderate one exhibits a large significant reduction in July. Similarly, relative humidity above 85% (HU85) shows a negative robust trend in both hills and plains. Overall, these results point to a warmer and drier environment for viticulture in the province of Treviso by the end of the century, underscoring the potential for more frequent hot extremes and prolonged dry periods, especially if global greenhouse gas emissions remain high.

	Moderate emissions scenario		Strong emissions scenario	
	Hill	Flat	Hill	Flat
Daily mean temperature (T_{mean} , °C)	1,9	1,8	4,2	4,2
Number of days with $T_{\text{max}} > 30^{\circ}\text{C}$ (days)	27,9	30,5	59,7	60,5
Number of days with $T_{\text{max}} > 35^{\circ}\text{C}$ (days)	8,2	12,3	30,9	39,5
Number of events with at least 5 days with $T_{\text{max}} > 30$ (# HWs)	1,5	1,3	2,0	1,1
Number of events with at least 3 days with $T_{\text{max}} > 35$ (# HWs)	0,9	1,5	3,0	3,6
Number of nights with $T_{\text{min}} > 18^{\circ}\text{C}$ (days)	27,9	25,0	54,1	52,3
Number of nights with $T_{\text{min}} > 20^{\circ}\text{C}$ (days)	26,3	21,8	56,9	51,1
Number of days with Precip > 5mm (days)	-3,8	-4,2	-8,7	-8,1
Mean number of consecutive days with Precip <1mm (days)	0,4	0,5	1,2	1,4
Precipitation sum for April (%)	-3,3	-1,8	-6,7	5,3
Precipitation sum for May (%)	-1,0	-5,0	-14,8	-18,6
Precipitation sum for June (%)	1,6	-2,0	-14,0	-18,8
Precipitation sum for July (%)	-30,6	-30,2	-49,9	-45,7
Precipitation sum for August (%)	-22,7	-24,4	-53,1	-51,6
Precipitation sum for September (%)	-12,0	-12,1	-23,6	-24,1
Number of days with relative humidity > 85% (days)	-6,5	-8,9	-11,0	-15,3

Table 9

As Table 7, but for changes in climate indices in April-September. Note that robust increasing changes are found for the temperature-related indices and CDD and decreasing ones for other precipitation-related indices and HU85 (coloured numbers).

3.2/2 Technical summary

Changes in long-term mean variables (Section 5.1) may not fully capture the impacts of climate change on climate-sensitive sectors such as viticulture. Therefore, it is essential to examine future changes in specific indicators that represent relevant conditions for the sector being analyzed; in this case viticulture.

This section presents the projected evolution of the indicators shown in Table 4 under two emissions scenarios: moderate and strong.

TEMPERATURE CHANGES

Projected changes in mean daily temperature (T_{mean}) during the growing season (April-September) are slightly greater than annual mean changes by the end of the century (cf. Fig. 23 and Fig. 21). The temporal evolution from 1990 to 2100 (Fig. 23, bottom panels) reveals a consistent warming trend throughout the century. Both scenarios follow similar warming trajectories until mid-century, after which the strong emissions scenario leads to substantially accelerated warming, roughly doubling the warming rate of the moderate scenario. This pattern is consistent across both hill and plain stations.

Figure 23

[Maps] Climate change signal for T_{mean} (2071-2100 with respect to 1990-2020), under two emission scenarios. Values correspond to the multi-model ensemble mean (the mean of the six climate models considered). [Time series] Temporal evolution of T_{mean} from 1990 to 2100 (average across hill -left- and plain -right- stations for the moderate (orange) and strong (purple) emissions scenario). The thick line represents the multi-model ensemble mean, the shading represents the model spread (full range of models). In all cases, the results are spatially averaged across the hill and plain selected stations (see Tables 1 and 2 for more details) and are restricted to the April-September period.

Technical summary

3.2/2 Technical summary

THRESHOLD EXCEEDANCES: TX30 AND TX35

The rise in temperature results in an increased frequency of TX30 (days with maximum temperature above 30°C) and TX35 (above 35°C), critical indicators for the viticulture sector. In particular, by the end of the century, TX30 is projected to increase by approximately 25 days under the moderate scenario and up to 70 days under the strong scenario (Fig. 24). This translates to nearly 90 days per year exceeding 30°C in hill stations and up to 100 days in plain stations under strong emissions. Under moderate emissions, these numbers reduce to about 55 and 65 days, respectively. TX35 also shows a marked increase: up to 10 additional days under moderate emissions and up to 40 days under strong emissions by the end of the century (Fig. 25). As with TX30, the increase is more pronounced in plain stations, and scenario differences become evident from the 2050s onward.

Figure 24

 As Fig. 23 but for TX30 in April-September.

Figure 25

 As Fig. 23 but for TX35 in April-September

HEATWAVE FREQUENCY: HW30 AND HW35

While TX30 and TX35 represent threshold exceedances, they do not necessarily capture the persistence of extreme heat conditions. HW30 and HW35 (heatwaves with daily maximum temperatures exceeding 30°C and 35°C, respectively) provide a measure of frequency and duration of prolonged warm conditions.

Both indices show an increasing trend, with HW30 reaching an average of 1-3 events per year (compared to the baseline period) by the end of the century (Fig. 26). In plain stations, HW30 increases similarly under both scenarios, while hill stations experience about one additional event under the strong emissions scenario. HW35 (Fig. 27) shows more spatial consistency, with an average increase of 3-4 events per year across all stations by 2100 (under strong emissions). However, uncertainty remains relatively high for both indices compared to the magnitude of change.

Figure 26

 As Fig. 23
 but for HW30 in
 April-September.

Figure 27

 As Fig. 23
 but for HW35 in
 April-September.

MINIMUM TEMPERATURE THRESHOLDS: TN18 AND TN20

Minimum temperature thresholds are also critical for grapevine development. TN18 and TN20 (number of days with minimum temperature above 18°C and 20°C, respectively) show notable increases (Fig. 28). By the end of the century, TN18 could reach approximately 110 days in hill stations and 95 in plain stations under strong emissions. TN20 may exceed 80 days in hill stations and remain just below 80 in plain stations. Scenario differences become more prominent from the 2050s onward.

Figure 28

 As Fig. 23
 but for TN18 in
 April-September.

Figure 29

 As Fig. 23
 but for TN20 in
 April-September.

Figure 30

 As Fig. 23
 but for PR5 in
 April-September.

PRECIPITATION INDICES: PR5 AND CDD

Projected reductions in total precipitation (Section 5.1) are reflected in derived indices such as PR5 (days with precipitation above 5mm) and CDD (consecutive dry days). PR5 declines by approximately 4 days under moderate emissions and up to 10 days under strong emissions by the end of the century (Fig. 30). In hill stations, this corresponds to a reduction from 35 to 32 or 26 days, respectively, and in plain stations from 32 to 28 or 24 days.

CDD increases modestly under strong emissions (Fig. 31), with an average of 2 additional dry days. By 2100, hill stations may see a rise from 3 to 5 consecutive dry days, and plain stations from 4 to 6.

Figure 31

 As Fig. 23
 but for CDD in
 April-September.

3.2/2 Technical summary

SEASONAL PRECIPITATION TRENDS

Monthly precipitation projections (Figs. 32 and 33) suggest notable decreases in July, August, and September—key months for vine growth and ripening. Under moderate emissions, reductions are expected in the range of:

- July: 20-40%
- August: 20-30%
- September: 10-20%

Under strong emissions, the reductions intensify to:

- July and August: 30-60%
- September: 10-30%

These changes are especially pronounced in hill stations (Fig. 34), with notable drying signals emerging in the final decades of the century. Overall, climate model ensemble spread remains larger than differences between emissions scenarios.

Figure 32
 Change (in %, 2071-2100 with respect to 1990-2020) in monthly accumulated precipitation in April-September under the moderate emissions scenario.

Figure 33
 As Fig. 32 but for the strong emissions scenario.

Figure 34
 Projected accumulated precipitation (expressed in mm) in July (upper panel) and August (lower panel), on average for the hill and plain stations considered (see Tables 1 and 2 for more details).

3.2/2 Technical summary

RELATIVE HUMIDITY THRESHOLDS: HU85

While average daily relative humidity (Section 5.1) shows minimal changes, exceedance of critical thresholds such as 85% (HU85) declines significantly (Fig. 35). A reduction of 6-10 days is expected under moderate emissions, and 8-16 days under strong emissions. Currently, HU85 occurs around 28 days/year in hill stations and 40 in plain stations (Fig. 19, Sec. 4.2). By 2100, these values are projected to decrease to:

- Hill stations: 22 (moderate) or 18 (strong) days.
- Plain stations: 35 (moderate) or 27 (strong) days.

Clear scenario-related differences begin from the 2060s onward.

Figure 35

As Fig. 23 but for HU85 in April-September.

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ANNEX 1 | Observations

The original set of observed records included 30 stations from ARPAV and 6 stations from Condifesa. They all have a sub-daily temporal resolution (Condifesa stations 3-hourly, except one which is 2-hourly and another 6-hourly; ARPAV is hourly). However, the work was performed on a daily basis because model data are available at daily time scales. Thus the daily mean, minimum and maximum temperature were calculated as well as daily mean relative humidity, and for precipitation the daily sum was obtained. Daily values were calculated only if there was no missing data in any of the sub-daily values. Thus, the number of missing values varies for each station and climate variable for the period of analysis, 1991-2020.

We considered the subset of stations with less than 34% of missing data per variable (i.e. 10 out of the 30 years, Fig. A1). Note also that some Condifesa stations recorded precipitation occurrence (binary variable) instead of precipitation amount. Those were excluded for the analysis. The final subset consisted of 24 stations for temperatures (20 from ARPAV and 4 from Condifesa), 21 stations for precipitation (all ARPAV) and 20 stations for relative humidity (17 from ARPAV and 3 from Condifesa).

Figure A1

Percentage of missing days in the period 1991-2020 for daily mean temperature, daily accumulated precipitation and daily mean relative humidity.

ANNEX 2 | Downscaling methodology

SCREENING OF PREDICTORS

We considered various predictor configurations of different complexity and involving different variables (see Table A1). Note that P6 was used by Gutiérrez et al. 2019 in the largest evaluation of empirical-statistical downscaling methods over European stations, taking Principal Components (PCs) explaining 95% of total variance. In the considered domain (44°N-48°N, 5°W-15°W) for reanalysis data (ERA5, Hersbach et al. 2020), 15 PCs are needed to retain 95% of the explained variance for P8 (finally selected predictor set). ERA5 is developed on a 25km x 25km grid, but was upscaled to a coarser resolution (200km x 200km) for consistency with the data provided by the global climate models considered (see Table 8).

Predictor ID	Variables
P1	U850, V850, Z850, T850, Q850
P2	U700, V700, Z700, T700, Q700
P3	U500, V500, Z500, T500, Q500
P4	Z500, Z850, T500, T700, T850
P5	Z500, Z850, T500, T700, T850, T2m
P6	Z500, Z850, T500, T700, T850, Q500, Q850, T2m
P7	Z500, Z850, T500, T700, T850, Q500, Q700, Q850, T2m
P8	U500, U700, U850, V500, V700, V850, Z500, Z850, T500, T700, T850, Q500, Q850, T2m

Table A1

Predictor sets considered. U, V: eastward and northward wind components respectively, Z: geopotential height, Q: specific humidity, T: air temperature. Numbers indicate vertical levels in the atmosphere, i.e. 500, 700, 850hPa levels and 2m represent 2-meter (surface).

Annex 2 | Downscaling methodology

CROSS-VALIDATION PROCEDURE

To avoid model overfitting and find the best predictor configuration for the indices of interest, we considered independent data to train/calibrate and test the statistical method. In particular, we used a 5-fold cross-validation framework in which the 30 year period was randomly split in 5 folds. Each fold (group of 6 years) was predicted based on the method that was calibrated upon the remaining 4 folds (24 years). This procedure was repeated 5 times to cover the entire period of analysis. See Figs. A2-A7 for the evaluation results in the cross-validation experiment for P8 (finally selected predictor set).

DOWNSCALING METHODS

At first, the analogs method was used since it provides physically consistent predictions for all predictands. However, it has a well-known limitation since it is not able to extrapolate beyond observed climate. To test its suitability to downscale the selected hazards we performed a second experiment, in which the 6 warmest years (considering the averaged temperature in all stations) were predicted using the remaining (colder) 24 years for calibration (i.e. a tailored 2-fold cross-validation framework), in order to mimic a warming world. Our results indicated that the number of tropical nights in the 6 warmest years was underestimated by the analogs method but better represented by linear regression in this experiment (see Fig. A8). Thus the analog method was used for precipitation and humidity and multiple linear regression for mean, maximum and minimum temperature.

Figure A2

Mean bias in Tmean (in °C, left) and HU85 (in days) in April-September for 1991-2020 in the cross-validation experiment. There is an overall small underestimation of Tmean and HU85 (up to 5 days less than observed, cf. Figs. 10 and 19).

Figure A3

Mean bias in TX30 and TX35 (days) in April-September for 1991-2020 in the cross-validation experiment. There is a small overestimation up to 5 days for TX30 and up to 2 days for TX35 (small relative to observed values, cf. Figs. 11 and 12).

Figure A4

Mean bias in the number of heat waves in April-September for 1991-2020 in the cross-validation experiment. The largest biases occur for HW35, of about plus/minus one heat wave. Note that this event rarely occurs in the observed climate (not even every year, cf. Fig. 13 and Table 6).

Figure A6

Mean bias in PR5 and CDD in April-September for 1991-2020 in the cross-validation experiment. PR5 is slightly overestimated up to 10 days (note that observed values range between 30-40 days) and the number of consecutive dry days are slightly underestimated (approximately one day less than observed, cf. Fig. 16).

Figure A5

Mean bias in TN18 and TN20 (days) in April-September for 1991-2020 in the cross-validation experiment. Both hazards are overestimated, up to 10 days for TN18 and 6 days for TN20 (cf. Figs. 14 and 15).

Figure A7

Relative biases (in %) in monthly (April-September) accumulated precipitation. Overall there is some underestimation for all months except in April. Biases are smaller than 20% (cf. Fig. 17).

Figure A8

Evolution of the number of tropical nights (TN20) for 1991-2020 for four selected stations. Observations (black) are compared to predictions obtained with the analog method (red) and linear regression (blue). In this experiment, the 6 warmest years (considering the averaged temperature in all stations), i.e. 1991, 2011, 2014, 2015, 2018, 2019 (purple circles) are predicted using the remaining (and colder) 24 years for calibration, and vice versa. Biases in TN20 for the 6 warmest years (depicted with purple circles) are shown in the titles. The bias reduction with linear regression compared to the analogs method is evident.

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Cover: Massimo Doro | Società Agricola Toni Doro
Inside pages: Arcangelo Piai
Image archive: pag.4, pag. 52

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